

Excited state intermolecular proton transfer reactions in few *N*-heterocyclic systems[†]

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Introduction

Among the complex organic molecules containing more than one basic center, the most basic and fundamental question is the site of protonation and the behavior of the ionic species in the solutions. The reasons being that the protonated molecules are intermediates in the synthetic organic chemistry and the knowledge of protonation sites plays a major role in developing the theory of the reaction mechanisms of acid-catalyzed reactions. Since the attack on the basic center by a proton is intimately connected with the concepts of inductive and resonance effects, charge density and bond polarization, it has also attracted the attention of theoretical chemists to develop the theories to explain the structural aspects of the species so formed. Because of these reasons and many others, the acid-base chemistry (or proton transfer reactions) is one of the most important processes in chemistry. It may be mentioned here that most of the books still cover the acid-base chemistry pertaining to the ground state (S_0). The acid-base reactions taking place in the excited states are still in the infancy state, although it has started gaining importance.

Proton transfer reactions can be divided into two broad categories. One, the excited state intermolecular proton transfer ($ESI_{er}PT$) and the other, excited state intramolecular proton transfer ($ESI_{ra}PT$) reactions. The former involves the transfer of a proton either from solute to solvent or from solvent to solute, whereas the latter involves only the rearrangement of the proton from one basic center to another within the molecule, i.e. formation of a phototautomer. Proton transfer reactions are very simple especially if it involves only one basic or one acidic center and have been studied extensively in the ground state¹⁻³. On the other hand, the proton transfer reactions studied in the excited states are still not that popular in the graduate course curriculum, even though these reactions are equally important in understanding the fundamentals of photochemistry and find lot of utility in the field of applied photochemistry⁴⁻⁸. For example, $ESI_{er}PT$ reactions have been used to understand the proton hydration dynamics^{9,10}, studied with the help of pH¹¹ and pOH¹² jump

experiments. Proton transfer indicators have also been used as probes to understand the environments of the micelles^{13,14}, reverse micelles^{15,16}, cyclodextrins¹⁷⁻²⁰, proteins²¹⁻²³, and films. On the other hand, the molecules undergoing $ESI_{ra}PT$ have been found to be very useful dyes used in tunable lasers²⁴, photochromic material²⁵, high-energy radiation detectors²⁶ and polymer stabilizers^{27,28}.

Romani *et al.*²⁹ pointed out that the dynamics of excited state prototropic reactions of the multibasic centers cannot be reliably investigated by a single technique, as each method works well for a single acidic/basic center. The disagreement between different methods is a signal of the complex character of these systems, complicated by the interlocking of several ground and excited state acid-base equilibrium. However, some generalizations can still be made regarding the pH effect on the photophysics of these molecules. Thus the present review article only deals with the proton transfer reactions of the molecules possessing more than one protonation site, establishing the site and structure of the ionic species so formed, both in the S_0 and S_1 states. Brief description of the history and the theoretical procedures available to establish and to predict the structure of the ionic species is also be given.

Weber's³⁰ observation that the spectral characteristics of the molecules as a function of acid-base strength are different in S_0 and S_1 states, were interrelated with the electronic redistribution followed by the excitation to higher state. In 1950, Forster³¹ formulated a procedure, commonly known as Forster's cycle, to calculate the pK_a value of a given equilibrium in the excited state (pK_a^*) using the S_0 state pK_a value and the absorption or/and fluorescence spectra of the molecule. The pK_a^* values thus obtained are also called as thermodynamic acidities/basicities constants of these reactions. The equation derived by Forster is given as

$$pK_a^* - pK_a = (N_{av}/2.2303 RT) (\bar{\nu}_{base} - \bar{\nu}_{acid}) \quad (1)$$

where N_{av} is the Avogadro number, R the gas constant, T the temperature in absolute, and $\bar{\nu}_{base}$ and $\bar{\nu}_{acid}$ are the 0-0

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

energies (cm^{-1}) of the base and its conjugate acid, respectively. Validity of the assumptions involved in this method has been considered from time to time³²⁻³⁴ and attempts have been made to relate the redox potential to the $\text{p}K_a^*$ and the electronic energy³⁵.

Weller³⁶ proposed another method, known as fluorimetric titration method, to calculate the $\text{p}K_a^*$ for the acid-base equilibrium of a molecule. Based on the steady state approximations, one can derive kinetic equations and thus can calculate the kinetic and spectroscopic parameters. Depending upon the values of the radiative decay rates of the respective acidic and basic species, and rates of protonation and deprotonation reactions, the fluorimetric titration curve may give a ground, excited or both (stretched sigmoid curve) $\text{p}K_a$ values. Thus apriori, it is very difficult to predict that the fluorimetric titration will give rise to the $\text{p}K_a^*$ value or not.

Theoretical calculations

Acid-base strengths of molecules in their ground states and in solutions are basically related to the resonance (also called mesomeric) and inductive effects. The inductive effect, understood as a polarization effect, is always present whenever an acidic or basic center is linked to a group, which also enters into quantum mechanical resonance with it. The efforts have always been there to quantify these effects and to study the relative importance of one over the other. One can find a number of examples, given in a review by Liler⁴, where experimental results have been used to quantify the contributions of these effects independently to the $\text{p}K_a$ values.

Most of the theories, which are used to predict the site of protonation of the basic center or to correlate the $\text{p}K_a$ values of the prototropic reactions with the physical parameters, concern with these reactions in the S_0 state. These theories have been extended to the excited singlet state by taking configuration interactions (CI) into account, but the results obtained should be treated cautiously. Most of the molecular orbital calculations (e.g. molecular mechanics³⁷, AM1^{38,39} etc. are compiled in the QCMP 137, MOPAC6/PC program or Hyperchem program). These programs are used to calculate the total energies of the respective protonated species by determining the bond energies of the σ - and π -bond frameworks under isolated conditions (non-polar environments). Although some efforts have been made to separate out the magnitude of the resonance energy from the inductive effect, it should still be treated carefully.

For example, the increased acid strength of the phenol ($\text{p}K_a = 10$) over the alcohols ($\text{p}K_a = 15-16$) is partly due to the inductive effect of the benzene (as the sp^2 hybridized

carbon atoms are more electronegative than the sp^3 hybridized and thus possesses better electron-withdrawing capacity) (1a) and partly due to the quantum mechanical resonance (1b) effect which delocalizes the negative charge of the anion over the complete framework of the species. The resonance effect will lead to the increase in the charge den-

sity at the *ortho* and *para* positions of the benzene ring and thus may become potentially competing sites for protonation with the oxygen atom. In the S_0 state, there is no evidence that any protonation takes place at these carbon sites and phenols are known to contain the OH group. This suggests that the resonance effect may not be very important in the S_0 state and the negative charge, which generally resides on the most electronegative atom, does so predominantly in the phenolate ion. However in the excited state, it has been shown^{40,41} that the resonance effect of the electron donor substituents increases the charge density at a particular carbon atom of the aromatic ring. This leads to the very facile electrophilic protonation of this carbon atom shown by the deuterium exchange, and also it leads to the proton-induced fluorescence quenching. This has been substantiated by the fact that the rate constants for this quenching have been correlated (although the correlation coefficient $r < 0.8$) to the π -charge densities at the appropriate C-atoms in the excited state of the aromatic compounds, calculated by using an SCF-MO-CI method. Similarly, Wan and Shukla⁴² discussed many examples where the site of protonation, especially at the carbon basic center, has been explained qualitatively using simple HMO theory in the excited singlet state.

The values of the energies of the respective protonated species (if more than one basic center is present in the molecule) in the S_1 state can also be calculated by taking into account the configuration interactions (CI). The complete optimization of the geometry and its energy depends upon the number of CI taken into account and the size of the molecule. Charge densities at different basic centers and the respective energies of the protonated species if more than one basic center is present in the molecule thus obtained by these methods have been successfully used to predict the site of protonation in a multi-basic center. However, simple correlations between ΔpK and the calculated electron density increase on protonation center are not successful. The correlation fails also for the case of predicting relative ground state $\text{p}K_a$ values, e.g. the simple

calculations give large electronic charge densities on the nitrogen of quinoxaline than for its isomer phthalazine (2,3-diazanaphthalene), whereas the latter is more basic in the S_0 state ($pK_a = 3.47$ versus 0.56 for quinoxaline).

Many alternative theoretical approaches for finding the relative basicity of possible protonation sites in a molecule have been developed. One of these is the calculation of the electrostatic potentials that these sites create in the space around them⁴³. In this method, the molecular wave function enables the calculation of the electrostatic potential $V(r)$ for a various points in a molecule, which would attract a point charge q at a distance r . The coulombic interaction energy qV represents then, to the first approximation, the true energy of interaction. However, this method neither takes into account the polarization of the molecule by the charge nor of the possible changes in the geometry at the site of protonation upon proton addition.

Waluk *et al.*^{44,45} developed semi-empirical approach where they showed that a semi-quantitative correlation exists between ΔpK_a and calculated charge density change in the whole aromatic ring. This approach implicitly takes into account the contribution of the atoms not directly involved in the proton transfer reaction. The importance of such contribution was demonstrated by applying the concept of an effective valence electron potential as a reactivity index⁴⁵ for the protonation reaction for several aza heterocyclic molecules in the S_0 state. In this method, the effective atomic potential can be interpreted as measuring the ease of partly removing an electron from the center in question. The potential should thus correspond to the negative of the local binding energy of a valence electron of the aza-nitrogen⁴⁵. Thus the pK_a values can be closely related to the proton affinities, which in turn depend upon the effective potential energy of the valence electrons on aza nitrogen. Higher the potential energy, the more energy is released during protonation and higher is the pK_a value for the protonation process. Eqn. (2) gives a nice correlation between the pK_a value and the effective potential (W),

$$pK_a = C + 10 W \text{ (eV)} \quad (2)$$

where C is a constant characteristic for the isoconjugate series ($C \approx 125$ for azabenzenes, ≈ 122.5 for azanaphthalenes and the standard error of estimate $\approx 0.5 pK_a$ unit).

The other very useful and effective method is to correlate the pK_a values with the average local ionization energy $I(r)$, on the molecular surface, also known as molecular electrostatic potential mapping⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸. $I(r)$, introduced as a use-

ful property for analyzing chemical reactivity, is defined within the framework of self-consistent-field molecular orbital (SCFMO) theory by eqn. (3),

$$I(r) = \sum_i \frac{\rho_i(r) |\epsilon_i|}{\rho(r)} \quad (3)$$

where $\rho_i(r)$ is the electronic density of the i -th molecular orbital at the point r_i , ϵ_i the orbital energy and $\rho(r)$ the total electronic density. $I(r)$ can be interpreted as the average energy needed to ionize an electron at any particular point r in the space of a molecule. Thus this procedure also considers the charge densities at the particular basic center of interest plus the effect of charges of the rest of the atoms in the molecule by defining global minima. The greater the depth of the global minima, the greater is the chances of protonation on the basic center. The advantage of this method is that not only it constructs the molecular electrostatic potential surface in the S_0 state, but also it can draw the molecular electrostatic potential surface in the excited singlet state.

All these semi-empirical methods discussed so far refer these calculations to the structures in the gas phase or under isolated conditions (non-polar solvents). When these structures are placed into a solvent, interactions will take place with the medium. These interactions may modify significantly the relative stability picture that emerges from these calculations. Nature of the medium determines to a certain degree the kind of ionic species that is experimentally observed. In certain cases where the stability of the two cations are nearly similar, one may end up in getting the isomeric mixture of two, or depending upon the nature of the solvent, one or other isomer may be favored over the other. Further, for the protonating reactions, which depend upon the polarizability effects, the rates of protonation are also medium-dependent because the protonating agent in various media can be more or less polarizing. It may also happen that in some cases where rates of protonation at one site are faster than at the other site, it may lead to the transient formation of a less stable protonated species and over the period of time it may lead to the more stable protonated species at equilibrium. Thus it may be mentioned here that the results obtained by the above mentioned theoretical methods should be treated cautiously. The energies of the solvated species in the S_0 and S_1 states can be estimated by taking into account the dipole-dipole interactions between the dipoles and the solvent according to^{49,50}

$$E_i(\text{solv}) = E_i - [\mu^2 / (4\pi\epsilon_0 a^3)] f(\epsilon) \quad (4)$$

where $E_i(\text{solv})$ and E_i are the solvated and gas phase energies, μ is the dipole moment in the respective state, a the

Onsager cavity radius and

$$f(\epsilon) = (\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1) \quad (5)$$

ϵ is the static dielectric constant.

Intermolecular proton transfer reactions

Nitrogen being the most common basic center, systems containing two or more nitrogen atoms have been studied extensively, both in the S_0 and S_1 states. This small review will only cover the *N*-heteroaromatic systems because the emission from these molecules in general is observed in the UV/visible region, which can be analyzed easily. Although there can be many possible combinations of nitrogen hetero atom present in the system with other hetero atom, this small review will only cover nitrogen hetero atom present in the aromatic ring as =N–.

Photophysics of simple *N*-heterocyclic aromatics, e.g. pyridine, quinoline etc. and their monocations (MC) have been studied extensively⁶. It is well established that the pK_a values for the MC-N equilibrium of these systems are ~ 5 in the S_0 state. The neutral molecules are non-fluorescent because of $n \pi^*$ as the lowest state. The MC's are fluorescent as $\pi \pi^*$ is the lowest energy state in these species and =N–atom becomes stronger base on excitation to S_1 state.

The simplest systems containing more than one *N*-hetero atom are either imidazole (2) or pyrazole (3). In 2, lone-pair of electrons on N1 forms part of the aromatic sextet and thus behaves like an acid, whereas N3 atom behaves like a base. The pK_a value for the protonation is 6.99 and is a stronger base as compared to pyridine (5.23). Owing to the presence of electron withdrawing N1 atom, it was expected that N3 would have been a weaker base than pyridine. The higher basicity of imidazole has been attributed to the resonance stabilization of the symmetrical cation 2c. Similarly 3, an isomer of 2, is also a *N*-hetero aromatic system, in which N1 atom donates the pair of electrons to the aromatic sextet. Alternatively, conjugation may be thought to occur in 3a, which would tend to enhance the basicity of N2. The pK_a value of 2.52, similar to that of pyrazine (1,2-diazabenzene) (2.3) does not depict the increase in the charge

density at N2. Both of the molecules are less basic than pyridine (5.23), which may be attributed to the neighboring nitrogen atom effect. Similar effect is also noted when two nitrogen atoms present are *para* to each other (see later). Photophysics of these molecules and their MC have not been studied in detail because the absorption spectra of these molecules are in the far-UV region (~ 230 nm). Photophysics of some of the phenyl derivatives have been studied and the data is given in Table 1⁵¹. The results (Table 1) are consistent with the fact that the presence of electron-withdrawing group, like phenyl, decreases the basicity of the basic center, and electron-donating group like methyl, increases the basic character. Further, N3 atom becomes stronger base in the S_1 . The ground state pK_a values observed from the fluorimetric titration method suggests that rates of protonation or deprotonation of MC-N equilibrium are smaller than those of the radiative decay rate constants of the respective conjugate acid-base pair.

Table 1. Absorption band maximum ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{ab}}$, nm), fluorescence band maximum ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{fl}}$, nm) of the neutral and MC of some pyrazoles and pK_a and pK_a^* of the MC-N equilibrium

Molecule*	$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{ab}}$		$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{fl}}$		pK_a	pK_a^*	
	Neutral	MC	Neutral	MC		Abs.	Fluo.
Pyrazole	210	214	–	–	2.48	4.37	–
DMP	215	219	–	–	4.38	6.13	–
PDP	245	234	309	312	2.27	–1.76	3.03
DPMP	250	248	388	–	1.48	0.64	13.95
TPP	251	274	372	–	–0.39	6.44	9.48
MPP	248	254	302	312	2.61	4.61	4.72
DPP	252	268	339	346			

*DMP = 3,5-dimethylpyrazole; PDP = 1-phenyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazole; DPMP = 1,5-diphenyl-3-methylpyrazole; TPP = 1,3,5-triphenylpyrazole; MPP = 3(5)-phenyl-5(3)-methylpyrazole; DPP = 4,5-diphenylpyrazole.

Photophysics of benzimidazole (BI, 4) and its derivatives have been studied extensively^{52–60}, both owing to the assessable region of the spectra and forming an integral part of vitamin B-12⁵³. Because of the presence of electron-withdrawing benzo group, BI is less basic ($pK_a = 5.53$) as compared to that of imidazole (6.99). Similar to imidazole, the site of protonation is N3 (4c). It is well established that the long wavelength absorption band (~ 277 nm) is localized on the benzene ring and the short wavelength absorption band (~ 240 nm) is localized on the imidazole ring, whereas in case of 2-phenyl substituted BI's, the long wavelength absorption band originates from the phenyl ring and BI acts as perturbation. The absorption spectra of the MC's are hardly affected. This helps in assigning the site of protonation when the nitrogen atom is also present in the benzo ring, as the protonation of the latter nitrogen atom leads to

large red-shift in the absorption and fluorescence spectra of the neutral species.

Fluorescence studies have shown that $\pi \pi^*$ is the emitting state in BI (fluorescence quantum yield, $\phi_f = 0.71$). Different views^{60,61} are used to explain the large and small Stokes shifted fluorescence spectra from the MC's. Detailed studies have resulted in the following conclusions in case of MC's of the BI's. (i) Charge transfer and $\pi \pi^*$ states are nearly degenerate. Electron-withdrawing groups in the imidazole ring and electron donating groups in the benzo ring stabilizes the charge transfer state more than $\pi \pi^*$ state. (ii) The small Stokes shifted fluorescence band is assigned to the $\pi \pi^*$ state and large Stokes shifted fluorescence band is assigned to charge transfer state. These results are confirmed from the effect of solvents on the fluorescence spectra of the MC's. (iii) Depending upon the nature of the BI's, the fluorescence spectra of the respective MC can be either small Stokes shifted or large Stokes shifted or dual emission can be observed. Table 2 gives the spectral characteristics of some of the BI derivatives and pK_a of their MC-N equilibrium^{60,61}.

Table 2. Absorption band maximum (λ_{\max}^{ab} , nm), fluorescence band maximum (λ_{\max}^f , nm) and the pK_a and pK_a^* values of the MC-N equilibrium

Molecule	λ_{\max}^{ab}		λ_{\max}^f		pK_a	pK_a^*	
	Neutral	MC	Neutral	MC		Abs.	Fluo.
BI	274	274	290	360	5.53	–	–
1-MeBI	277	274	301	292, 360	5.7	4.60	3.55
2-MeBI	279	274	290	284, 368	5.9	4.74	4.37
5,6-MeBI	285	281	300	298, 380	5.4	4.35	4.92
2,5,6-MeBI	286	282	302	298, 380	6.0	4.94	5.07
1-Et-2-MeBI	280	276	292	286, 361	6.3	5.22	5.00
1-Me-2-PhBI	287	285	352	359	5.2	4.69	6.19
2-ClCH ₂ BI	277	275	304	358	4.0	3.45	5.0
2-Cl ₂ CHBI	278	274	297	375	4.1	3.00	5.0
5-Cl-2Cl ₃ BI	292	300	354	–	0.3	2.20	–
2-F ₃ CBI	281	280	340	410	0.6	0.30	1.6
2-CIBI	279	277	304	–	2.1	1.60	0.0
2-NCCH ₂ BI	278	275	290	390	3.5	2.70	3.5
2-PhBI	299	295	350	358	5.23	3.53	6.57
2-CH ₂ NH ₂ BI	278	279	291	–	8.1	–	–
2-CH ₂ OHBI	278	275	284	372	4.2	3.6	–
N-Me-2-CH ₂ OHBI	282	275	286	370	4.4	2.5	–

Photophysics of the aromatic molecules and their prototropic species containing more than one nitrogen atom is similar to that of simple nitrogen containing aromatics, i.e. fluorescent nature of the neutral and its MC is governed by the energies of the $n \pi^*$ and $\pi \pi^*$ states. In quinoxaline (**5**)⁶¹, the protonation of the ring nitrogen atoms occur stepwise and the pK_a values are given on the arrows of the Scheme. Quinoxaline is less basic than pyridine, but similar to in basic strength when compared with pyrazine⁶² (**6**) ($pK_a = 0.6$). This is due to the presence of second nitrogen atom at the *para*-position of **5**, which will lead to the formation of exactly equivalent dipolar structure (**5'**) in the non-ionized molecule and this may strengthen the resonance of these species at the expense of their respective MC's. These molecules (quinoxaline, phenazine, pyrazine etc.) are analogous to azabenzene, which is very weak base for the same reason.

Similar to pyridine, **5** is also non-fluorescent in water at 298 K⁶³, but fluorescent at 77 K, whereas the MC and dication (DC) are non-fluorescent both at 298 and 77 K, a behavior different when compared with the MC of pyridine or phenyl substituted pyridines. Thus the photophysics of these kinds of molecules and their prototropic species in general is studied by taking their derivatives, mostly aromatics rings, which are fluorescent in nature and thus can shed some light on the behavior of the ionic species in the S_1 state.

Waluk *et al.*^{64,65} used the idea of effective valence electron potential calculations to predict the site of protonation in case of 2-amino- (**7**) and 2,3-diaminoquinoxaline (**8**). Effective valence electron potential calculations predicted that MC in both cases will be formed by protonating the NH₂ group both in S_0 and S_1 states. Dication in case of **7** is formed by protonating the N-atom *meta* to NH₂ group rather than

protonating the N-atom *ortho* to NH₂ group. On the other hand, the charge density data predicted the other ways. The results of the former calculations agree with what has already been observed for azabenzene, i.e. the N-atom basicity of an aromatic aza compounds may be very sensitive to the electronic long-range effects. In case of **7**, the presence of positively charged NH₃⁺ group in the vicinity of N1 strongly reduces the basic character of N1 relative to N4. Of course, the DC in case of **8** will be formed by protonating the second NH₂ group and trication by protonating any of the N-atom as both the N-atoms are symmetrical to both the NH₃⁺ groups.

Santra and Dogra⁶⁶ also showed that the simple correlation between the charge density data also fails to predict the site of protonation in quinoxalinone (**9**), *N*-methyl-2-quinoxalinone (**10**) and 2-methoxyquinoxaline (**11**). Instead of using the effective valence electron potential, Santra and

Dogra⁶⁶ used the electrostatic potential energy mapping for all the three molecules. These calculations have shown that in case of **11**, the MC is formed by protonating the N-atom, which is *ortho* to methoxy group as N1 is more reactive (-148 kJ mol^{-1}) than N4 (-74 kJ mol^{-1}). On the other hand, in case of **9** the MC is formed by protonating the more reactive carbonyl oxygen ($-209.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) than the >NH group ($-104.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$). Of course, the DC in each case is formed by protonating the N4 atom. Similarly, the first protonation site in quinoxaline-2,3(1*H*, 4*H*) dione (**12**) and 1,4-*N,N*-dimethylquinoxaline-2,3-dione⁶³ (**13**) is also carbonyl oxygen atom rather than >NH group. In these molecules, the

second site of protonation is also the carbonyl oxygen.

Lastly, the molecules like 2-(2'-methoxyphenyl)-3*H*-imidazo[4,5-*b*]pyridine (**14**)⁶⁷ and 2-(2'-methoxyphenyl)-1*H*-imidazo[4,5-*c*]pyridine (**15**)⁶⁸ are isomers and differ in the position of nitrogen atom in the benzo ring (i.e. the nitrogen atoms are in the separate rings). Spectral characteristics, time-correlated emission and electrostatic potential energy mapping have shown that only one kind of MC is formed in **15**, by protonating the imidazole ring N-atom, whereas in **14**, less polar MC ($\mu = 2.7 \text{ D}$) is formed by the addition of proton at imidazole ring N-atom under smaller ionic strength (high pH). As the ionic strength increases (pH decreases), another kind of MC (more polar, $\mu = 9.1 \text{ D}$) is formed by protonating the pyridine N-atom at the expense of less polar MC. In other words, position of the N-hetero atom on the ring plays a major role in the spectral characteristics of the neutral and the MC of the isomer molecules. The reason being that the reactivity difference of the imidazole N-atom and pyridine N-atom is not very large in case of **14** in comparison to **15**.

Conclusions

Fluorescence spectroscopy combined with semi-empirical quantum mechanical calculations can be a useful tool in predicting and assigning the proton addition to a specific N-hetero atom in the multi-basic molecules.

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